

Model	Model Attributes	Node Attributes	Edge Attributes
MW-FCM	'model' string	'value' double	'weights' string
FTCM	'model' string 'min_operator' boolean	'value' double 'dummy' boolean	'weight' double
TL-GFCM	'model' string	'lower_value' double 'middle_value' double 'upper_value' double 'dummy' boolean	'lower_weight' double 'middle_weight' double 'upper_weight' double
GFCM	'model' string	'lower_value' double 'middle_value' double 'upper_value' double	'lower_weight' double 'middle_weight' double 'upper_weight' double
FCM4DRV	'model' string	'value_pmf' string	'weight_pmf' string
FGCM	'model' string	'lower_value' double 'upper_value' double	'lower_weight' double 'upper_weight' double
IV-FCM	'model' string	'lower_value' double 'upper_value' double	'lower_weight' double 'upper_weight' double
IS-FCM	'model' string	'value' double	'lower_weight' double 'upper_weight' double
iFCM-II	'model' string	'membership_degree' double 'nonmembership_degree' double	'membership_degree' double 'nonmembership_degree' double
FCM-NAS	'model' string	'value' double 'class' string	'weight' double
FCM	'model' string 'memory' boolean	'value' double	'weight' double

Table 1: Attributes for each model

1 Supplementary Material

1.1 Supplementary Tables

1.2 Supplementary Figures

1.3 Additional Algorithms

The following algorithms specify the remaining transformations. They are similar to algorithms shown in the article, which were selected to showcase different approaches. In Algorithm 11, note that the conversion from GFCM to FCM or TL-GFCM to FTCM requires defuzzifying the data, which originates from triangular membership functions. However, the specific functions may be unknown, hence the center of gravity method cannot be used. To overcome this limitation, our algorithm takes the average of the three values in line with prior work Rahmani et al. (2016); this is equivalent to the center of gravity method when the triangular membership function is symmetric.

References

Rahmani, A., F. Hosseinzadeh Lotfi, M. Rostamy-Malkhalifeh, and T. Allahviranloo. 2016. "A new method for defuzzification and ranking of fuzzy numbers based on the statistical beta distribution". *Advances in Fuzzy Systems* vol. 2016.

Algorithm 1 *FCM to IV-FCM or FGCM* : $(G, target) \mapsto G_{target}$

```

1: for  $node \in V(G)$  do
2:   // Create lower and upper value attributes
3:    $node_{value}^{lower} \leftarrow node_{value}$ 
4:    $node_{value}^{upper} \leftarrow node_{value}$ 
5:   Remove the value node attribute
6: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
7:   // Create lower and upper weight attributes
8:    $edge_{weight}^{lower} \leftarrow edge_{weight}$ 
9:    $edge_{weight}^{upper} \leftarrow edge_{weight}$ 
10:  Remove the weight edge attribute
11:  $G_{type} \leftarrow target$  // Assigns the graph's type as an IV-FCM or FGCM
12: return  $G$ 

```

Algorithm 2 *IV-FCM to iFCM-II* : $(G) \mapsto iFCM-II$

```

1: for  $node \in V(G)$  do
2:   if  $(node_{value}^{lower} < 0) \vee (node_{value}^{upper} < 0)$  then
3:     return  $\emptyset$  // iFCM-II is only defined on non-negative values
4:   // Create membership and nonmembership degree attributes
5:    $node_{degree}^{membership} \leftarrow node_{value}^{lower}$ 
6:    $node_{degree}^{nonmembership} \leftarrow 1 - node_{value}^{upper}$ 
7:   Remove lower value and upper value node attributes
8: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
9:   if  $(edge_{weight}^{lower} < 0) \vee (edge_{weight}^{upper} < 0)$  then
10:    return  $\emptyset$ 
11:    $edge_{degree}^{membership} \leftarrow edge_{weight}^{lower}$ 
12:    $edge_{degree}^{nonmembership} \leftarrow 1 - edge_{weight}^{upper}$ 
13:   Remove lower weight and upper weight edge attributes
14:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'iFCM-II'$ 
15: return  $G$ 

```

Algorithm 3 *FCM-NAS to FCM* : $(G) \mapsto FCM$

```

1: for  $node \in V(G)$  do
2:   // If it is a need node, add an edge to itself with a weight of 1 to add memory
3:   if  $node_{class} = 'Need'$  then
4:      $E(G) \leftarrow E(G) \uplus \{(node, node, 1)\}$ 
5:   Remove the class node attribute
6:  $G_{memory} \leftarrow False$  // Set FCM memory attribute to False
7:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'FCM'$ 
8: return  $G$ 

```

Algorithm 4 *IS-FCM to IV-FCM or FGCM* : $(G, target) \mapsto G_{target}$

```

1: for  $node \in V(G)$  do
2:   // Create lower and upper value attributes
3:    $node_{value}^{lower} \leftarrow node_{value}$ 
4:    $node_{value}^{upper} \leftarrow node_{value}$ 
5:   Remove the value node attribute
6:  $G_{type} \leftarrow target$ 
7: return  $G$ 

```

Algorithm 5 *FCM to FCM-NAS* : $(G) \mapsto FCM-NAS$

```
1: for  $node \in V(G)$  do
2:   if  $G_{memory}$  then // If the FCM has memory, make each node a Need
3:      $node_{class} \leftarrow 'Need'$ 
4:   else // Otherwise, make each node a State
5:      $node_{class} \leftarrow 'State'$ 
6:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'FCM-NAS'$ 
7: return  $G$ 
```

Algorithm 6 *iFCM-II to IV-FCM* : $(G) \mapsto IV-FCM$

```
1: for  $node \in V(G)$  do
2:   // Create lower and upper value node attributes
3:    $node_{value}^{lower} \leftarrow node_{degree}^{membership}$ 
4:    $node_{value}^{upper} \leftarrow 1 - node_{degree}^{nonmembership}$ 
5:   Remove membership degree and nonmembership degree node attributes
6: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
7:   // Create lower and upper weight edge attributes
8:    $edge_{weight}^{lower} \leftarrow edge_{degree}^{membership}$ 
9:    $edge_{weight}^{upper} \leftarrow 1 - edge_{degree}^{nonmembership}$ 
10:  Remove membership degree and nonmembership degree edge attributes
11:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'IV-FCM'$ 
12: return  $G$ 
```

Algorithm 7 *FCM to MW-FCM* : $(G) \mapsto MW-FCM$

```
1: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
2:    $edge_{weights} \leftarrow edge_{weight}$  // Assign weight to weights attribute as a string (e.g., '5')
3:   Remove weight edge attribute
4:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'MW-FCM'$ 
5: return  $G$ 
```

Algorithm 8 *MW-FCM to FCM* : $(G) \mapsto FCM$

```
1: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
2:    $edge_{weight} \leftarrow \sum edge_{weights}$  // Set weight as sum of weights
3:   Remove weights edge attribute
4:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'FCM'$ 
5:  $G_{memory} \leftarrow False$ 
6: return  $G$ 
```

Algorithm 9 *IS-FCM to FCM* : $(G) \mapsto FCM$

```
1: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
2:    $edge_{weight} \leftarrow (edge_{weight}^{lower} + edge_{weight}^{upper}) \div 2$  // Set weight as midpoint of interval
3:   Remove lower weight and upper weight edge attributes
4:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'FCM'$ 
5:  $G_{memory} \leftarrow True$ 
6: return  $G$ 
```

Algorithm 10 *FCM to IS-FCM* : $(G) \mapsto IS\text{-FCM}$

```
1: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
2:   // Create lower and upper weight attributes
3:    $edge_{weight}^{lower} \leftarrow edge_{weight}$ 
4:    $edge_{weight}^{upper} \leftarrow edge_{weight}$ 
5:   Remove the weight edge attribute
6:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'IS\text{-FCM}'$ 
7: return  $G$ 
```

Algorithm 11 *GFCM to FCM or TL-GFCM to FTCM* : $(G, target) \mapsto G_{target}$

```
1: for  $node \in V(G)$  do
2:   // Take midpoint of/defuzzify triangular fuzzy number
3:    $node_{value} \leftarrow (node_{value}^{lower} + node_{value}^{middle} + node_{value}^{upper}) \div 3$ 
4:   Remove lower value, middle value, and upper value node attributes
5: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
6:    $edge_{weight} \leftarrow (edge_{weight}^{lower} + edge_{weight}^{middle} + edge_{weight}^{upper}) \div 3$ 
7:   Remove lower weight, middle weight, and upper weight edge attributes
8:  $G_{type} \leftarrow target$ 
9: if  $target = 'FCM'$  then
10:   $G_{memory} \leftarrow False$ 
11: return  $G$ 
```

Algorithm 12 *FCM to FCM4DRV* : $(G) \mapsto FCM4DRV$

```
1: for  $node \in V(G)$  do
2:    $node_{pmf}^{value} \leftarrow P(X = node_{value}) = 1$  // Create discrete probability mass function
3:   Remove value node attribute
4: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
5:    $edge_{pmf}^{weight} \leftarrow P(X = edge_{weight}) = 1$ 
6:   Remove weight edge attribute
7:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'FCM4DRV'$ 
8: return  $G$ 
```

Algorithm 13 *FCM4DRV to FCM* : $(G) \mapsto FCM$

```
1: for  $node \in V(G)$  do
2:   // Set the value as the expected value of the probability mass function
3:    $node_{value} \leftarrow E(node_{pmf}^{value})$ 
4:   Remove value pmf node attribute
5: for  $edge \in E(G)$  do
6:    $edge_{weight} \leftarrow E(edge_{pmf}^{weight})$ 
7:   Remove weight pmf edge attribute
8:  $G_{type} \leftarrow 'FCM'$ 
9:  $G_{memory} \leftarrow False$ 
10: return  $G$ 
```

Figure 1: The graphical user interface on macOS